

PUBLIC CONSENSUS AS A MECHANISM OF LEGITIMATION OF POLITICAL AUTHORITY

Mirzaahkmedov K.M.

Professor at National University of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Political Sciences (DSc)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14273232>

Abstract. *In the given article, the author revealed a conceptual analysis of the important political mechanisms that manifest a unique form of the state administration system: the content of the concepts of legality and legitimacy, the specific technologies of the formation of legality and legitimacy in ensuring the stability and integrity of political power and the need for long-term existence. Also, he showed the effective directions of legal and legitimate relations in the support of the political power by the society as well as strengthening of trust in its activeness.*

Keywords: *legitimacy, legality, political power, state management, administrative personnel, administrative staff, human resources, government system, leader.*

It is important to suggest that achievement of any positive result without mutual cooperation of people, public associations, different organizations in all spheres of society is a bit challenging. Today's globalization processes have a great impact on the need for such cooperation.

Civil society institutions and the state are equally interested in mutual cooperation. If government agencies can resolve current issues in society through mutual cooperation, civil society institutions will achieve their program goals and enhance their image and influence in the political field.

Definitely, this natural instinct, which encourages people to live together, work in harmony and live life as a whole, served them to save themselves from natural disasters and protect them from wild animals, having already reached a level of comfortable existence in the early times of human existence.

The great thinker Abu Nasr Farabi expresses the importance of cooperation in achieving human happiness with the following thoughts: "A city that unites people who help each other in order to achieve true happiness is a virtuous city, a community of people united in order to achieve true happiness is a virtuous community which is necessary for achieving happiness" [1]. Consensus (Latin *constio* - community of feelings, thoughts, mutual understanding) [2] is the agreement of a significant majority of members of any community on the most important principles of political structure, values, distribution of power and rights in society. Consensus is a universal principle of democracy that allows for resolving and preventing contradictions and conflicts, easing tensions in society, and reaching agreement on contentious issues. The principle of consensus assumes that the opinions of both the majority and the minority are taken into account. This is facilitated by a high standard of living, respect for human rights and freedoms, tolerance in society, the presence of institutional forms of conflict resolution developed by the state, and the ethnic and religious homogeneity of society.

The consensus theory was also developed by A. Tocqueville, who substantiated the conclusion that society exists only when the majority of people in society have common views on various problems and common habits. The values and ideals that prevail in a particular society predetermine human behavior. The commonality of these values forces the individual to adapt to the positions of other people, thereby achieving equilibrium in the social system.

The consensus theory was developed in the 1950-1960s in the works of T. Parsons, E. Durkheim, and others and is based on the belief in the ability of a person to prevent various political conflicts and conduct discussions in a peaceful environment. In particular, we can see a comparative analysis of scientific theories put forward regarding consensus in the following table [3].

Representatives	Content of approach
Bowman S., Ambrosini V.	Consensus is manifested as a common or collective understanding and represents the level of development of directions of strategic development of organizations, departments and institutions by leaders in the field of strategic management.
Grinyer P., Norbern D.	Consensus is a statistically significant degree of collective agreement, which can be calculated in the form of an assessment of the degree of functional agreement among employees.
Bourgeois L..	Consensus is the agreement of the political elite to share the goals and objectives of competition
Wooldridge B., Floyd S.	Consensus is the result of commitment, interest and recognition of the strategy of an organization, institution, company by middle managers.
Knight D.	Consensus is the level of mutual understanding between group members, as well as the agreement or similarity of mental models of members of departments regarding the strategies of the organization, institution, office.
Kellermans F.	Consensus is a collective understanding of strategic priorities among top, middle, and lower (operational) level managers.
Gonzalez-Benito J.	Consensus is an agreement on methods of political competition and strategic goals

In democratic societies, three objects of agreement (consensus) are usually distinguished. The first level of consensus shows that a certain society shares the same values and goals. This means the agreement of the majority of members of society on basic norms and principles.

The second level of consensus determines the rules of political behavior and conduct, which are enshrined in the basic laws-constitutions. This means the consent of the majority to recognize political power, election results and governance structures.

The third level of consensus gives priority to the problem of confrontation of power. Political consensus is the agreement of the majority regarding the basic forms of organization of political power (for example, recognition of a certain form of government). In this case, disagreements may arise not about the form of government, but about the attitude towards members of the government (the political elite). There are also certain levels of the consensus factor, which we can see in the table below:

Besides that, the third object of consensus is considered the weakest level, since the attitude towards individual members of the government and its policies can change very quickly, both from the side of society and from the side of the state. Therefore, the implementation of administrative

reforms, the application of institutional and functional changes, as well as the regular introduction of democratic governance methods will further expand the possibilities of consensus.

Possible objects of agreement	Consensus levels
System of political values: freedom, equality, etc	Consensus or value at the level of society
Normative resources: legal procedures, contractual provisions	Consensus at the level of the political regime
At the government level: members of the government and their policies	Political consensus

As an example, reflecting on the experience of democratic transformations in their country, Spanish political scientists emphasize that the process of building a "permanent civil peace" is ensured by achieving three consensuses:

1. Consensus on the past, including the rejection of the "evil hunt" and national reconciliation between the "winners" and "losers" in the civil war of 1936-1939;
2. Determination of the temporary order of the relevant standards of democratic development processes;
3. Recognizing the principle of rapid change of governing bodies and guarantee the rights of minorities [4].

This is not only the work of government bodies to create a fair public order that meets the interests of the majority of the population in the territory of any country. World history shows that neither the state, nor the family, nor market relations can resolve social conflicts separately. Only consensus, that is, constructive dialogue and agreement of various forces in the socio-political sphere, can provide people with opportunities to live a decent life. One of the most important features of consensus is the guarantee of a free exchange of ideas, the freedom of the parties to present their normative value systems.

A brief review of the history and development of consensus theory shows that all theories and ideologies that existed before represented only the interests of a particular class or social group. Consensus theory asserts that harmony and social stability can be achieved in society only when the interests of all social groups involved in the relationship are harmonized. Therefore, this theory is not a theory of a particular class, but a theory that represents the interests of all interacting social groups through their harmonization. Harmonization of the interests of social groups is an important condition and basis for the formation and development of civil society.

Consensus essentially means agreement. But it differs from the agreements that existed before the twentieth century in that it has created a new effective practice for reaching an agreement. According to him, parties whose interests do not coincide with each other should, when entering into interaction and negotiations, first of all make concessions to each other. Moreover, they should try to find a solution that will satisfy everyone, at least, will not cause opposition from any side. Finding such a solution means reaching consensus. German sociologist J. Habermas interprets the concept of consensus as an alternative to democracy [5]. In his interpretation, the democratic method divides the community and society into two parts: the majority and the minority. Consensus unites the divided community and society. This is achieved not by determining the majority opinion on the problem being solved, but by finding a solution that does

not contradict all parties. To achieve consensus, parties whose interests and approaches are not very compatible must try to find a solution that neither party opposes.

The theory of social consensus was also widely studied by the American sociologist T. Parsons. He studied the mechanisms of interaction between subjects using his scientific approaches. In this case, he attached particular importance to the process of transforming generally accepted norms and patterns of behavior into internal motives for activity. Drawing attention to the fact that equilibrium and consensus are the most important features of the normative state of a social system, T. Parsons paid great attention to the processes of control and regulation of this state. In his opinion, it is these currents that protect society from unpleasant conflicts. In his research, the problem of consensus is studied in an aspect directly related to the search for mutually agreed upon options for action. Such interaction is based on the mutual expectations of partners, that is, on the actions and results that they expect from each other. Also, the French scientist Louis Auguste Blanqui, criticizing capitalist society, interpreted the dynamics of historical development as the spread of enlightenment and the formation of cultural and social relations on this basis. It was formed on the basis of the theory of social action, social solidarity, social consent and social cohesion as theoretical conceptual foundations of social consent. According to M. Weber, traditional behavior is a model of behavior that has developed in cultural traditions and is not amenable to analysis and rational criticism. The importance of this type of movement is determined by the fact that everyday behavior of people often occurs in this way. In such actions, customs and loyalty to customs, understood at different levels, play a decisive role.

According to M. Weber, consensus has become a real force in political decision-making, since the management decision is made without conflicting interests of all stakeholders. As a result, when a certain level of consensus is reached in the course of consultations between policymakers regarding the goals, priorities, methods and means of implementing strategic programs, it can be assumed that they will be effectively implemented.

It should be emphasized that the consensus theory created by T. Parsons, E. Durkheim and J. Habermas in the middle of the twentieth century gave a great impetus to the widespread use of social partnership. This theory replaced the theory of social contract and began to serve as the theoretical and methodological basis for social partnership.

In modern political science, consensus in the narrow sense is a method of making political decisions characterized by a clearly expressed political will of the majority and the absence of objections from at least one of the participants. This shows that the consensus method is effective in resolving various disputes and conflicts. Consensus in the broad sense is also a public recognition of the ways and means of political management and integration, i.e. "public consent". The higher the level of public approval in society, the more stable the political system. Only then will the real legitimization of political governance be realized through political consensus. Before the rights and freedoms of the individual become the basis of public consent, it is necessary for the individual to realize his or her rights and to act as a contender for freedom and dignity. In this case, it is required that the property rights of citizens be protected by society and become a universal measure of legal freedom and equality.

All participants in social exchange are recognized as free and officially equal subjects who realize and protect their interests. At the same time, various interests in society are coordinated and a balanced process of interaction is formed. In this way, social consensus is achieved and relations of social partnership are resolved.

The structure of social consensus includes traditions, components of political value, socio-psychological relations, etc.

All components of social consensus directly affect social pluralism. Moreover, the order of social pluralism that does not reflect national culture, traditions, values, goals, cannot be stable and legitimate. If it is illegitimate, it will be changed or destroyed by society itself. It is clear that the interaction of pluralism and consensus is a complex conflict process that causes many problems.

Political contradictions and conflicts are an inevitable companion of politics, an attribute of the political process. Consequently, on the basis of a civilized political culture, there is a need to create fair standards that would allow constructive dispute resolution, regulation of the political process and the dynamics of the entire society.

Consensus values are recognized by society and form the basis of active sociality. It is known that Western society relies on strictly defined instrumental values. The problem of technology here is a problem of life. Any means must be based on the factors of legality and legitimacy. But the diversity of political goals preserves the possibility of introducing positive changes into the social system.

Considering pluralism through an integrative prism and combining it with the idea of consensus differentiation raises another pressing issue – understanding societies with different forms of consensus and pluralism. In particular, in the context of multiculturalism, polytonicity and polyconfessionalism, the question of the coexistence of social communities with different values and norms of life inevitably arises.

In short, public consensus and legitimization of political power is the process of public recognition of political power, explanation and justification of the political system in order to convince society of the fairness of the political system. Legitimacy, expressing the subjective and emotional attitude of the people to political power, serves to ensure the stability of this power, the performance of its functions, obedience, trust and political participation. Therefore, public consensus and social cooperation, considered to be the values of sustainable development of society, are very important as a prerequisite for the formation of the legitimacy of political power.

The legitimacy of political power can be considered as a kind of public consensus, which mainly reflects the agreement associated with the structure of the state, the procedure for the formation of state bodies, the processes of implementing management functions. In turn, the dominant method of political power is determined by the basic consensus achieved in society. Naturally, any modern democratic state presupposes the formation of rational legal legitimacy.

REFERENCES

1. Abu Nasr Farabi. City of Virtuous People. - Tashkent, "Generation of the New Century", 2016. - P.285.
2. Mamasiddikov M.M., Otajonov A.A. and others. Development and improvement of mechanisms for establishing effective public control over the activities of government agencies in our country / Monograph. Collective of authors. Editor-in-chief, Ph.D., prof. Mamasiddikov M.M. - Tashkent. "Press Lesson". 2020. – P.278.
3. Tumenova S.A., Mambetova F.A., Pshigosheva A.Yu. On the implementation of strategies for innovative development of the regional economic space // Socio-economic systems in the context of global transformations: problems and development prospects: collection of

scientific papers of the International scientific and practical conference, Nalchik, May 27-28, 2021. - Nalchik: FGBOU VO Kabardino-Balkarian SAU. 2021. -P. 308-312.

4. Political processes: a textbook / A.V. Glukhova; Voronezh State University - Voronezh: Publishing and Printing Center of Voronezh State University, 2009.
5. Khakimov G.T., Akhmedova M.T. The role of public control in public administration of the Republic of Uzbekistan // Development and improvement of the mechanism of effective public control over the activities of state bodies to ensure human rights in our country: collection of materials of the republican scientific and practical conference. - Tashkent: 2018. - P.245.